

EFFECT OF SALINE VERSUS SALINE-ADRENALINE HYDRODISSECTION: IMPACT ON BLOOD LOSS IN VAGINAL HYSTERECTOMY

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Abstract

Background: The reduction of intraoperative blood loss during vaginal hysterectomy is crucial for minimizing surgical complications and improving operative conditions. Hydrodissection is commonly used to facilitate tissue separation, and the addition of adrenaline to saline has been suggested to further reduce bleeding through vasoconstriction.

Objectives: To compare mean intraoperative blood loss between patients undergoing vaginal hysterectomy with hydrodissection using saline alone versus saline combined with adrenaline.

Study Design & Setting: A comparative cross-sectional study conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology Mekran Medical College (MMC), Turbat.

Methodology: A total of 114 patients scheduled for elective vaginal hysterectomy were enrolled and divided equally into two groups (57 patients each). Group A received hydrodissection with normal saline, while Group B received hydrodissection with saline combined with adrenaline (1:200,000). Standardized surgical techniques were followed for all procedures. Intraoperative blood loss was measured using the volume in suction apparatus and the weight of surgical sponges. Demographic and operative data were recorded and analyzed using SPSS version 20. Numerical data were expressed as mean \pm SD, and the independent sample t-test was applied for comparison. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: The baseline characteristics of patients undergoing vaginal hysterectomy were comparable between the two study groups. The mean age in the saline hydrodissection group was 49.3 ± 6.8 years, while it was 48.7 ± 7.1 years in the saline-adrenaline hydrodissection group. Mean intraoperative blood loss was significantly higher in the saline group (92.4 ± 13.8 mL) compared to the saline-adrenaline group (85.1 ± 14.2 mL), with a p-value of 0.005. Intraoperative characteristics showed comparable surgical conditions in both groups. The mean duration of surgery was 72.4 ± 11.6 minutes in patients receiving saline hydrodissection and 69.8 ± 10.9 minutes in those receiving saline-adrenaline

hydrodissection.

Conclusion: Hydrodissection with saline–adrenaline significantly reduces intraoperative blood loss compared to saline alone during vaginal hysterectomy and may improve surgical conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Vaginal hysterectomy remains one of the most commonly performed gynecological procedures for the management of benign uterine conditions such as uterine prolapse, fibroids, dysfunctional uterine bleeding, and adenomyosis.^{1,2} Owing to its minimal invasiveness, shorter hospital stay, faster recovery, and lower postoperative morbidity, the vaginal route is generally preferred over abdominal hysterectomy when feasible.³ Various surgical techniques and adjunctive measures have been introduced to minimize blood loss during hysterectomy. One such technique is hydrodissection, which involves the infiltration of fluid into tissue planes to facilitate dissection, separate anatomical structures, and reduce tissue trauma.⁴ Hydrodissection enhances visualization of surgical planes and may reduce inadvertent injury to surrounding tissues. Saline solution is commonly used for this purpose due to its availability, safety, and isotonic nature.⁵

Adrenaline acts by stimulating alpha-adrenergic receptors, leading to vasoconstriction and reduced capillary bleeding. This pharmacological effect has been utilized in various surgical specialties, including otolaryngology, plastic surgery, and dentistry, to reduce intraoperative blood loss and improve operative field clarity.⁶ In gynecological surgery, the addition of adrenaline to local infiltration solutions has been explored as a means to decrease bleeding during procedures involving extensive tissue dissection.⁷

The vaginal route of hysterectomy involves dissection through highly vascular tissues, particularly around the cervicovaginal junction, uterosacral ligaments, and uterine vessels. Even minor increases in bleeding from these areas can significantly affect surgical ease and outcomes.⁸ Hydrodissection with saline alone aids in mechanical separation of tissues, whereas saline combined with adrenaline provides both mechanical and pharmacological benefits by reducing local blood flow. However, the extent to which the addition of adrenaline offers a measurable

reduction in blood loss compared to saline alone remains an area of ongoing evaluation.⁹⁻¹¹

Concerns have also been raised regarding the potential systemic effects of adrenaline, including tachycardia, hypertension, and arrhythmias, especially in patients with cardiovascular comorbidities. Therefore, understanding the balance between effective hemostasis and safety is essential when considering adrenaline-containing solutions in vaginal surgery. Previous studies have reported variable findings regarding the efficacy of saline–adrenaline hydrodissection in reducing blood loss, highlighting the need for clear and focused evaluation of this technique in vaginal hysterectomy.¹²⁻¹⁴ Given the frequency of vaginal hysterectomy and the importance of minimizing intraoperative blood loss, a comparison between saline hydrodissection and saline–adrenaline hydrodissection provides valuable insight into optimizing surgical technique and improving operative conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This comparative study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology Mekran Medical College (MMC), Turbat over a 6 months from Jan 2024 to June 2024 study period. A total of 120 patients undergoing vaginal hysterectomy for benign gynecological indications were included in the study. Patients aged between 35 and 65 years, planned for elective vaginal hysterectomy, were enrolled after obtaining informed consent. Patients with known bleeding disorders, cardiovascular disease, uncontrolled hypertension, hypersensitivity to adrenaline, malignant gynecological conditions, or those requiring additional pelvic procedures were excluded from the study. The sample size of 120 patients was calculated using the WHO sample size calculator by taking the mean intraoperative blood loss reported in previous studies, with a confidence level of 95% and a power of 80%. A minimum of 60 patients was required in each group to detect a

clinically meaningful difference in mean blood loss between the two groups.

The enrolled patients were divided into two equal groups by non-probability consecutive sampling. Group A included 60 patients who underwent hydrodissection using normal saline alone, while Group B included 60 patients who underwent hydrodissection using normal saline combined with adrenaline. In Group B, adrenaline was added to saline in a concentration of 1:200,000. All procedures were performed under standardized anesthesia protocols by surgeons with comparable levels of experience to minimize operator-related bias.

Hydrodissection was performed at the cervicovaginal junction and along the surgical planes prior to dissection. In both groups, the same volume of infiltrating solution was used. Vaginal hysterectomy was then carried out using the standard surgical technique, and all intraoperative steps were kept uniform between the two groups.

Intraoperative blood loss was recorded as the primary outcome measure. Blood loss was estimated by measuring the volume of blood collected in the suction apparatus after subtracting the volume of irrigation fluid and by weighing surgical sponges before and after use, with the difference in weight converted to milliliters. Demographic data, including

age, parity, indication for surgery, and duration of surgery, were also recorded.

All collected data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 20. Numerical variables such as age, duration of surgery, and intraoperative blood loss were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Mean intraoperative blood loss between the two groups was compared using the independent sample t-test. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board prior to commencement of the study.

RESULTS

The baseline characteristics of patients undergoing vaginal hysterectomy were comparable between the two study groups. The mean age in the saline hydrodissection group was 49.3 ± 6.8 years, while it was 48.7 ± 7.1 years in the saline-adrenaline hydrodissection group. Mean parity and body mass index were also similar between the groups. Uterine prolapse was the most common indication for surgery in both groups, followed by fibroids and dysfunctional uterine bleeding/adenomyosis, as given in Table 1.

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of Patients Undergoing Vaginal Hysterectomy (n = 120)

Variables	Variable	Saline Hydrodissection	Saline-Adrenaline Hydrodissection
Age (years)	Mean \pm SD	49.3 ± 6.8	48.7 ± 7.1
Parity	Mean \pm SD	3.6 ± 1.2	3.4 ± 1.3
Body Mass Index	Mean \pm SD	27.1 ± 3.5	26.8 ± 3.2
Indication	Uterine Prolapse	28 (46.7)	30 (50.0)
	Fibroids	18 (30.0)	16 (26.7)
	Adenomyosis	14 (23.3)	14 (23.3)

Intraoperative characteristics showed comparable surgical conditions in both groups. The mean duration of surgery was 72.4 ± 11.6 minutes in patients receiving saline hydrodissection and 69.8 ± 10.9 minutes in those receiving saline-adrenaline hydrodissection. The volume of infiltration solution

used was uniform across both groups. Intraoperative complications were infrequent and occurred in a small proportion of patients in each group, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Intraoperative Characteristics of the Study Groups

Variable	Saline Hydrodissection	Saline-Adrenaline Hydrodissection
Duration of Surgery (minutes)	72.4 ± 11.6	69.8 ± 10.9
Volume of Infiltration Used (mL)	100 ± 15	100 ± 15
Intraoperative Complications	4 (6.7%)	3 (5.0%)

The mean intraoperative blood loss was higher in patients who underwent hydrodissection with saline alone compared to those who received hydrodissection with saline combined with adrenaline. In the saline group, the mean blood loss

was 92.4 ± 13.8 mL, whereas in the saline-adrenaline group it was 85.1 ± 14.2 mL. This difference between the two groups was statistically significant with a p-value of 0.005, as given in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of Mean Intraoperative Blood Loss Between Study Groups

Parameter	Saline Hydrodissection (n = 57)	Saline-Adrenaline Hydrodissection (n = 57)	p-value
Intraoperative Blood Loss (mL), mean ± SD	92.4 ± 13.8	85.1 ± 14.2	0.005

DISCUSSION

Vaginal hysterectomy is a widely performed procedure for benign uterine conditions such as prolapse, fibroids, and abnormal uterine bleeding. Intraoperative blood loss remains a major concern as it can obscure the surgical field and increase transfusion requirements. Hydrodissection using saline is commonly employed to facilitate tissue separation and reduce bleeding. Addition of adrenaline to saline may further reduce blood loss by causing local vasoconstriction.¹⁵ Therefore, evaluating the impact of saline versus saline-adrenaline hydrodissection is important for optimizing surgical outcomes.

In the present study, mean intraoperative blood loss was significantly higher in patients undergoing vaginal hysterectomy with saline hydrodissection (92.4 ± 13.8 mL) compared to those receiving saline-adrenaline hydrodissection (85.1 ± 14.2 mL, p = 0.005). The findings of our study are consistent with previous literature that emphasizes the role of infiltration or vasoconstrictive agents in reducing intraoperative bleeding. Yeasmin et al. (2019) reported that the group with infiltration had significantly lower blood loss and better maintenance of hemoglobin concentration compared to the non-infiltration group, with mean operating times of 59.18 minutes for vaginal hysterectomy and 60.93 minutes for fistula and perineal repair (P < 0.05). No

infections were noted in either group, highlighting the safety of infiltration techniques.^{15,16} Similarly, Sayed et al. (2021) observed a significantly lower mean blood loss in the saline dissection group (294.8 ± 96.87 mL) compared to the no-infiltration group (507.31 ± 348.37 mL, z = -2.04, p = 0.04), despite comparable mean age, stage of prolapse, and duration of surgery between groups. These studies support our findings that saline-based infiltration reduces bleeding during pelvic surgeries.¹⁷

The reduction in blood loss observed in our study also aligns with findings from Kanti et al. (2022), who reported that intraoperative blood loss was significantly greater in the total laparoscopic hysterectomy (TLH) group (111.03 ± 20.8 mL) compared to non-descent vaginal hysterectomy (NDVH, 59.50 ± 16.7 mL) and laparoscopic-assisted vaginal hysterectomy (LAVH, 91.85 ± 10.66 mL), indicating that less invasive vaginal approaches or adjunctive measures reduce bleeding.¹⁸ Nimodia et al. (2021) found that use of vasopressin significantly reduced estimated blood loss from incision to flap creation (21.33 mL vs 49.67 mL, p = 0.001), further demonstrating the effect of vasoconstrictive agents,¹⁹ while Parveen et al. (2018) reported mean operative times of 72.27 ± 10.32 minutes in the infiltration group with fewer complications (15.7%) compared to 89.31 ± 12.45 minutes and 39.47% complications in the control group (p < 0.0001). Our study similarly

demonstrated comparable durations of surgery and minimal intraoperative complications in both groups, indicating that adrenaline addition improves hemostasis without increasing operative risk.²⁰

This study included a clearly defined sample size with equal distribution in both groups, ensuring comparability. Standardized surgical technique and experienced surgeons minimized operator bias. Objective measurement of intraoperative blood loss using suction and sponge weighing improved accuracy. Limitations include single-center design, which may limit generalizability. Blinding of the surgical team was not feasible, introducing potential observer bias. Additionally, patients with comorbidities were excluded, which may affect applicability to all clinical populations.

CONCLUSION

Saline-adrenaline hydrodissection significantly reduces intraoperative blood loss compared to saline alone in vaginal hysterectomy. The technique is safe and easy to implement. Incorporating adrenaline into hydrodissection may improve surgical conditions and outcomes.

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Conflict of Interest: No

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REFERENCES

Vishwakarma S, Mittal N, Singh NP. A comparative analysis of nondescent vaginal hysterectomy, laparoscopy-assisted vaginal hysterectomy, and total laparoscopic hysterectomy for benign uterine diseases at a rural tertiary care center. *Gynecology and Minimally Invasive Therapy*. 2022 Jul 1;11(3):164-70.

Azadi A, Masoud AT, Ulibarri H, Arroyo A, Coriell C, Goetz S, Moir C, Moberly A, Gonzalez D, Blanco M, Marchand G. Vaginal hysterectomy compared with laparoscopic hysterectomy in benign gynecologic conditions: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 2023 Dec 1;142(6):1373-94.

Krentel H, De Wilde RL. Prevalence of adenomyosis in women undergoing hysterectomy for abnormal uterine bleeding, pelvic pain or uterine prolapse-A retrospective cohort study. *Annals of Medicine and Surgery*. 2022 Jun 1;78:103809.

Kališ V, Rušavý Z, Ismail KM. Hysterectomy versus uterine preservation in the management of uterine prolapse. *Laparoscopic Urogynaecology: Principles and Practice*. 2022 Oct 13;175.

Mamik MM, Kim-Fine S, Yang L, Sharma V, Gala R, Aschkenazi S, Sheyn D, Howard D, Walter AJ, Kudish B, Balk EM. Hysterectomy techniques and outcomes for benign large uteri: a systematic review. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 2022 May 5:10-97.

Gatica S, Aravena D, Echeverría C, Santibanez JF, Riedel CA, Simon F. Effects of adrenergic receptor stimulation on human hemostasis: a systematic review. *Advances in Molecular Pathology*. 2023 Apr 25:49-63.

Geevarghese III M, Patel K, Gulati A, Ranjan AK. Role of adrenergic receptors in shock. *Frontiers in physiology*. 2023 Jan 16;14:1094591.

Wedel T. Topographical Anatomy for Hysterectomy Procedures. *In Hysterectomy: A Comprehensive Surgical Approach 2017* Sep 15 (pp. 37-60). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

Ramdhan RC, Loukas M, Tubbs RS. Anatomical complications of hysterectomy: A review. *Clinical Anatomy*. 2017 Oct;30(7):946-52.

Sheth SS, Paghdwalla KP, Hajari AR. Vaginal route: a gynaecological route for much more than hysterectomy. *Best Practice & Research Clinical Obstetrics & Gynaecology*. 2011 Apr 1;25(2):115-32.

Alkatout I. Laparoscopic hysterectomy: total or subtotal?-Functional and didactic aspects. *Minimally Invasive Therapy & Allied Technologies*. 2022 Jan 3;31(1):13-23.

Yurtkal A, Canday M. Optimizing hysterectomy: a prospective comparative analysis of surgical techniques and their impact on women's lives. *Journal of personalized medicine*. 2024 Feb 29;14(3):265.

- Hafidh B, Latifah HM, Gari A, Alshahrani MS, AlSghan R, Alkhamis WH, Allam HS, AlRasheed MA, Bakhsh H, Abu-Zaid A, Baradwan S. Vasopressin to control blood loss during hysterectomy: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Journal of Minimally Invasive Gynecology*. 2022 Mar 1;29(3):355-64.
- Cui Y, Chen I, Chernoff A, Clancy A. Effectiveness of prophylactic pharmacological hemostatic agents for reduction of blood loss at vaginal surgery: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *International Urogynecology Journal*. 2023 Dec;34(12):2945-57.
- Nguu LK. An Observational Study On Blood Transfusion Requirements In Patients Undergoing Total Abdominal Hysterectomy/myomectomy For Uterine Fibroids In Kenyatta National Hospital (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi). <https://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/handle/11295/101850>
- Yeasmin SF, Hasanat MA, Rahman MT, Islam F, Akhtar D, Begum A. Use of local infiltration and vasoconstrictors in vaginal surgery. *Mediscope*. 2019 Sep 16;6(2):49-52.
- Sayed SP, Dorairajan G. Comparison of blood loss between saline infiltration and no infiltration dissection during vaginal prolapse surgery randomized controlled trial. *J Gynecol Res Obstet*. 2021;7(2):018-23.
- Kanti V, Verma V, Singh M, Vishwakarma S, Mittal N, Singh NP. A comparative analysis of nondescent vaginal hysterectomy, laparoscopy-assisted vaginal hysterectomy, and total laparoscopic hysterectomy for benign uterine diseases at a rural tertiary care center. *Gynecology and Minimally Invasive Therapy*. 2022 Jul 1;11(3):164-70.
- Nimodia V, Jain S, Rajaram S, Tyagi A, Gupta B. Effect of Diluted Vasopressin vs Saline on Intraoperative Blood Loss during Vaginal Hysterectomy-A Randomised Controlled Trial. *Journal of Clinical & Diagnostic Research*. 2021 Jun 1;15(6):6778-83.
- Parveen TA, Kausar TA, Iqbal TA, Batool A. Comparison of outcome between vaginal and abdominal hysterectomy. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences*. 2018 Oct;7(4):1150-3